

ENHANCING PATIENT EXPERIENCE: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF WAITING TIMES IN PHARMACY SERVICES AT A PREMIER CITY HOSPITAL'S OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT

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Abstract

The dissertation titled "**Enhancing Patient Experience: A Comprehensive Analysis of Waiting Times in Pharmacy Services at a Premier City Hospital's Outpatient Department**" was conducted over an 8-day period from January 29th to February 5th, 2024. The study aimed to analyze waiting times in the pharmacy department using observation, time study, and questionnaires, with 95 out of 260 patients participating in the questionnaire survey.

The study involved calculating the time spent on each step/activity, such as issuing prescriptions, handling/sorting out medicines, processing payments, and delivering medicines, to determine the total Turn Around Time (TAT) in the pharmacy department of the hospital. The main objectives of the study were to assess the total waiting time for patients, identify unavailable/out of stock medicines, and evaluate the performance and behavior of the pharmacy staff.

The study indicated the level of satisfaction of the patients and the attendees' experience in the pharmacy department. The findings suggest that reducing waiting times and improving the quality of services provided by the pharmacy staff could help increase hospital revenue. The research was based on interactions with patients, attendees, and pharmacy staff at a city-based hospital in Kolkata.

Key Words:

Hospital, patient, satisfaction, study, time study, pharmacy, turnaround time (TAT), waiting time, survey, questionnaire, process mapping, data analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The pharmacy department is a crucial component of a hospital, responsible for providing medications to nursing units, filling special prescriptions, and dispensing drugs to ambulatory patients and outpatients. It is always under the charge and direction of a professionally competent, legally qualified pharmacist and plays a vital role in the efficient functioning of clinical and administrative services within the hospital.

A significant portion of a hospital's total expenditures is allocated to pharmaceutical services, highlighting the need for careful attention to the efficiency of these services. A well-organized pharmacy has been proved to be a high revenue earner, even in smaller hospitals.

Patient waiting time in the pharmacy, defined as the duration from when a patient enters with a prescription to when they receive the prescribed medicines, significantly impacts the patient's experience/perception of service quality. Excessive waiting times can undermine pharmacy efficiency, leading to patient dissatisfaction and potential loss of patronage in a competitive healthcare system.

The primary goal of the pharmacy is to provide the right drug, at the right time, at the right cost, and at the right place to the right patient. Therefore, conducting a systematic study on patient waiting time in the pharmacy is essential to identify factors affecting waiting times and recommend ways to minimize delays, ultimately enhancing the patient experience.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the root causes of delay in getting medicines by calculating the average time taken for a patient or an attendee from the receipt of the prescription till the time the medicines are received from the pharmacy counter, categorized by specialty.
- To assess the patients' satisfaction level by the service of the pharmacy department.
- To calculate the waiting time/time lost due to non-availability of medicines across various specialties.
- To analyze the collected data statistically and derive some insights about the waiting times and patient experiences.
- To provide recommendations on how waiting times can be reduced and customer satisfaction increased within the pharmacy department.

Process map of the pharmacy operations system in the hospital:

Diagram 1: Process map of issuance of medicines from the Pharmacy

Methodology followed for the Research

This research is primary research conducted at the hospital premises and necessary data/information was collected on spot through a questionnaire survey as required. The details of the methodology followed are summarized below.

Sample Size: The study had a sample size of 260, out of which 95 individuals responded to the questionnaire. This provides a response rate of approximately 36.5%.

Data Collection Methods: The data for the study was collected using the following methods:

- Observation
- Stopwatch
- Interviewing the patients

Study Duration and Participants: The study was conducted over a period of one week and included only outpatients and their attendants.

With this information, it became necessary and important to consider the following points while evaluating the various observations:

Response Rate: The response rate of 36.5% may have implications for the generalization of the findings to the larger population. It's important to consider how representative the respondents are of the entire sample.

Data Collection Methods: The combination of observation, stopwatch use, and patient interviews provides a diverse range of data collection methods, which can offer a comprehensive understanding of the research subject.

Study Duration and Participants: Conducting the study over a week and focusing on outpatients may impact the general ability of the findings to the broader population.

Potential Biases: The use of interviews as a data collection method may introduce biases based on the interviewer's approach and the patients' responses. Additionally, the use of a stopwatch and observation may introduce observer bias.

Overall, while the data collection methods provide a comprehensive approach, the response rate and potential biases need to be carefully considered when interpreting the findings of the study.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Speciality-wise patient waiting time

SPECIALITY DEPARTMENT	TIME TAKEN (IN MINUTES)	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
INTERNAL MEDICINE	0 TO 10 MIN	20	21.05%
PAEDIATRIC	0 TO 09 MIN	18	18.94%
CARDIOLOGY	0 TO 08 MIN	16	16.84%
PULMONOLOGY	0 TO 08 MIN	16	16.84%
NEUROLOGY	0 TO 07 MIN	14	14.73%
PSYCHIATRY	0 TO 05 MIN	11	11.60%

TABLE 1: Patient waiting time in minutes in various departments

Fig 1: Patient waiting time percentage in various specialty department

INTERPRETATION: From the above pie chart shown as Fig.1, it is seen that the average time taken by internal medicine is maximum, and it is 10 minutes. This might be due to the excessive rush of patients in this department and also the list of medicines is much longer compared to other specialties. The average waiting time is found to be minimum in the case of psychiatry, being 5 minutes, as the rush of patients in this department is minimum and the list of medicines are also very less.

TIME OF THE DAY WISE	TIME TAKEN (IN MINUTES)	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
9AM-10AM	0 to 08 min	9	9.88

10-11AM	0 to 10 min	12	12.35
11AM-12PM	0 to 10 min	12	12.35
12PM-1PM	0 to 11 min	13	13.58
1PM-2PM	0 to 10min	12	12.35
2PM-3PM	0 to 09 min	11	11.11
3PM-4PM	0 to 08 min	9	9.88
4PM-5PM	0 to 08 min	9	9.88
5PM-6PM	0 to 07 min	8	8.62

Table 2: Patient Waiting Time in Minutes during Different Hours of the Day

Fig.2: Patient waiting time in percentage during different hours of the day

INTERPRETATION: From the above graph (Fig. 2) it is seen that the time taken for issuance of medicines at the pharmacy is maximum during the time period of 10am-12pm and 12pm-1pm . It is also observed that the rush of patients is maximum during this period whereas the time taken during the time period of 9am-10am and 5pm-6pm is minimum as the rush of patients during this period of time is also minimum.

Analysis of patient satisfaction at the pharmacy counter:

The number of patients who responded to the questionnaire was 95 out of 260.

Number of questionnaires distributed = 260

Response received = 95

Question NO1. How was your experience in the pharmacy counter?

Response Type	NUMBERS OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE (%)
SATISFIED	60	63.16
PARTIAL SATISFIED	25	26.31
NOT SATISFIED	10	10.53
Total	95	100

Table 3: Percentage wise patient experience in the pharmacy counter

Fig.3: Percentage Satisfaction Level of Patients on experience in the pharmacy counter

INTERPRETATION: From the above graph (Fig. 3) it is noted that 63.16% of patients and patient attendees are satisfied, 26.31% of patients and patient attendees are partially satisfied and 10.53% of patients and patient attendees are unsatisfied with their experience in the pharmacy counter. Reasons for partial satisfaction and nonsatisfaction of the patients are enumerated in the table below (Table 4) with number of respondents.

Table 4: No of partially satisfied and dissatisfied patients with reasons

Categories	Numbers	Reasons
Partially Satisfied	20	Had to wait for a long period of time to get medicine from the pharmacy
	5	Very high rush of patients in the pharmacy counter.
Unsatisfied	7	Did not get all the prescribed medicines from the pharmacy.
	3	Too much waiting time to get the medicine from the pharmacy.

Question No 2. Were all the medicines available?

Response	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
YES	60	73.68%
NO	35	26.31%

Table 5: Responses on availability of medicines in the Pharmacy

Fig 4: Responses in percentage on the availability of medicines in the pharmacy

INTERPRETATION: From the above graph (Fig. 4), it is seen that 73.68% of patient and patient attendees got all the medicines which were prescribed in the prescription and 26.31% of patient and patient attendees did not get all the medicines which were prescribed in the prescription. From the previous graph (Fig. 3), it is seen that the analysis here corresponds to the total of partially satisfied and dissatisfied patients.

Medicines	Specialist	Number of Patients	Total
Roliflo OD 4mg tab	Internal Medicine	4	14
Tab HCQ S200	Internal Medicine	3	
Augmentin 1gm	Internal Medicine	2	
Lucifin cream	Internal Medicine	1	
Nexpro RD	Internal Medicine	2	

Dvion capsule	Internal Medicine	2	
Urimaxflohal	Pulmonology and critical care	3	3
Syp. Crocin DS 5ml	Pediatric	7	18
Calpol 25C	Pediatric	5	
IPV Vaccine	Pediatric	3	
Nasivion mini 0.01 prop	Pediatric	3	

Table 6: Non-availability of medicines at the pharmacy as per the prescriptions issued by specialty departments

Fig.5: Non-availability of medicines in percentage for various specialties

INTERPRETATION: From the above graph (Fig. 5), it is clear that the highest non-availability of medicines are pediatric prescriptions accounting for 51.43% , followed by internal medicines accounting for 40%, and pulmonology and critical care medicines non-availability accounting for the rest of 8.57% .

Question No 3. Were you satisfied with the behavior of the staff of the hospital?

RESPONSE	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
SATISFIED	75	78.95%
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	20	21.05%
NOT SATISFIED	0	0%

TABLE 7: Patient satisfaction by the behavior of the hospital staff

Fig. 6: Patient satisfaction level in percentage by the behavior of the hospital staff

INTERPRETATION: From the above figure (Fig. 6) it is established that 78.95% of patient and patient attendees are satisfied by behavior of the staff of the hospital, whereas 21.05% of patient and patient attendees are partially satisfied and there is no unsatisfied patient or patient attendees.

From table 8 below, it is observed that partial satisfaction of patients or the patient attendees is mainly due to lack of information from the hospital staffs regarding appointment schedule with a particular doctor.

CATEGORIES	REASONS	NUMBERS
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	Staffs not keeping patients well informed about the delay in appointment schedule of doctors.	8

Table 8: Partially satisfied patient with reasons

Question NO 4. Are you satisfied with the service provided by pharmacists?

TABLE 9: Patient satisfaction by the service of the pharmacist

RESPONSE	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
SATISFIED	50	52.63%
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	20	21.05%
NOT SATISFIED	25	26.31%

Fig 7: Patient percentage satisfaction level by the service of the pharmacist.

INTERPRETATION: From the above graph (Fig. 7), it is seen that 52.63% of patients and patient attendees are satisfied by the behaviour of the pharmacist, 21.05% of patients and patient attendees are partially satisfied on the same count and 26.31% are not satisfied at all.

CATEGORIES	REASONS	NUMBERS
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	Had to wait for more than 8 minutes to procure the medicines from the pharmacy counter.	15
	Had to wait for 10 minutes in the pharmacy counter to procure medicines.	5
NOT SATISFIED	Had to wait for more than 13-15 minutes in the pharmacy counter to procure medicines.	15

	Had to wait for 18-20 minutes in the pharmacy counter to procure the medicines.	10
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Table 10: Partially satisfied and not satisfied patient with reasons

Question No 5. Did the pharmacist listen to you carefully?

RESPONSE	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
SATISFIED	85	89.47%
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	10	10.53%
UNSATISFIED	0	0.00%

TABLE 11: Patient satisfaction by the listening of the pharmacist

Fig. 8: Percentage responses on satisfaction about the listening of the Hospital pharmacy staff

INTERPRETATION: From the above figure (Fig. 8) it is seen that 89.47% of patients and patient attendees are satisfied by the way the pharmacist listened to their problems, 10.53% of patients and patient attendees are partially satisfied by the way the pharmacist listened to their problems and none of the patients were unsatisfied by the way the pharmacists listened to their problems.

CATEGORIES	REASONS	NUMBERS
PARTIALLY SATISFIED	The pharmacist was in a hurry to explain in detail about the medicines so explained in brief.	3
	A lot of rush in the pharmacy counter so couldn't ask in detail about the medicines.	7

Table 12: Partially satisfied patient with reasons about the listening of the pharmacy staffs

ANALYSIS OF REASONS FOR WAITING TIME IN PHARMACY

Reasons	Numbers	Percentage
Medicines not available	35	28.69%
Inadequate availability of systems in billing counter	45	36.89%
Payment card Swipe error	10	8.20%
Issue of change of medicines	20	16.39%
System error	12	9.84%

TABLE 13: Reasons of Waiting in pharmacy

FIG.9: Percentage of various reasons for waiting in pharmacy

INTERPRETATION: From the above figure (Fig. 9) it is established that 28.69% of the waiting time is due to non-availability of medicines, 36.89% is due to inadequate availability of systems in the billing counter, 8.20% is due to payment cards swiping error, 16.39% is for issue of changed medicines and 9.84% for system error.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Based on the study it is recommended that the hospital should have dedicated counters for specific medicines and to facilitate faster issuance and deliver of medicines it is advisable to have some hospital staffs posted at the entrance of the pharmacy counter to guide patients/patient attendees to their respective counters for medicines and billing.
- Furthermore, an additional staff member at the billing counter would facilitate smoother operations and reduce waiting times in the pharmacy.
- To expedite the billing process, it is recommended to increase the number of systems available at the pharmacy counter. Moreover, staff members at the billing counter should needs to be properly trained and efficient so that billing is completed quickly, thereby streamlining the entire process and reducing waiting times in the pharmacy department.

CONCLUSION:

The study emphasizes the importance of faster patient services at the pharmacy by optimizing every step of the process from patient entry to issuance of medicines.

The research study's results have organizational applications and can be utilized to enhance the internal administration of the pharmacy department within the hospital.

The findings revealed that most patients were partially satisfied with pharmaceutical services at the pharmacy, with long waiting times being a major cause of dissatisfaction. It was observed that most patient waiting times in the hospital were due to delays in the dispensing procedure due to internal issues. Therefore, efforts should be made to reduce the time spent on these components of dispensing, allowing more time for guiding patients to identified counters and efficient billing.